

Solvent Extraction of Calcium(II) with Alizarin into 1-Octanol

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In view of the biological importance of calcium^I, it is apparent that a rapid and selective method for the separation of Ca^{II} from other elements is required. Eu^{III}, Cr^{III}, In^{III} and Sc^{III} have been extracted using alizarin reagent. However, alizarin has not been used for the solvent extraction of Ca^{II}. The present work describes a method for the solvent extraction and radiochemical separation of Ca^{II} employing alizarin reagent.

Results and Discussion

The extraction coefficient value (Table 1) revealed a maximum *E* value of 14.5 at a pH of 9.5. The percentage extraction was found to be greater than 92.0% in the pH range 9.0–10.0. *E* value was found to decrease in the more acidic range (Table 1). The reproducibility of the method was found to be 8.5%. The percentage extraction was found to be maximum for an equilibration time of 8.0 min under the experimental conditions.

TABLE 1 – EFFECT OF pH AND TIME OF EQUILIBRATION

pH	Extraction coefficient (<i>E</i>)	Time of equilibration min
2.0	0.02	8.0
4.0	0.03	8.0
6.0	0.47	8.0
7.0	0.52	8.0
8.0	7.24	8.0
9.0	12.3	8.0
9.5	14.5	8.0
10.0	12.6	8.0

1-Octanol and amyl alcohol gave better extraction coefficient values than other solvents. 1-Octanol was preferred as the phase separation was quicker and

cleaner. The extraction coefficient value (*E* in parenthesis) revealed a decreasing trend : 1-Octanol (14.5) > amyl alcohol (12.4) > pentanol (2.14) > cyclohexanone (1.85) > isobutanol (1.77) > n-butanol (1.04) > ethyl acetate (0.13) > methyl isobutyl ketone (0.04) > amyl acetate (0.02) > hexane (0.01). Isopropanol, 1-propanol and pyridine were found to be miscible with the aqueous phase. In case of diethyl ether, chloroform, benzene, toluene, carbon tetrachloride and nitrobenzene, no phase separation was observed.

Effect of foreign ions : The effect of sodium, potassium or ammonium salts on the extraction coefficient value revealed that 100 mg of bromate, iodate, thiocyanate, chlorate, chloride, cyanide and thiocyanide; 50 mg of iodide, nitrite, chromate, acetate, bromide, sulphate and thiourea; 25 mg of nitrate, sulphite, carbonate, borate; 10 mg of tartrate, biphosphate, thiosulphate, arsenite, bicarbonate and dichromate, do not decrease the *E* value of Ca^{II}. Oxalate lowered the *E* value and the interference was removed by decomposing with 5 ml of concentrated HNO₃ and HCl prior to the extraction of Ca^{II}. The interference of phosphate and tungstate was removed by precipitating with ammonium molybdate and HCl respectively. Of the cations studied, Cs^I, Ba^{II}, As^V, S^{VI}, Ir^{IV}, P^V, Rb^I, W^{VI}, K^I, Sb^{III}, Cr^{III}, Se^{IV}, Tl^I, As^{III}, Na^I, Te^{IV} and Pd^{II} were extracted between 1 and 10%. Mo^{VI}, Hg^{II}, Cd^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II}, Ag^I, Cu^{II}, Eu^{III}, La^{III}, Fe^{II}, Fe^{III}, Sc^{III}, In^{III}, Mn^{II}, Ce^{III}, Ce^{IV}, Au^{III}, Pt^{IV}, Sn^{II}, Sn^{IV}, Zr^{IV} and Ru^{III} were extracted to greater than 10%. The interference of Mo^{VI}, Hg^{II}, Cd^{II}, Ag^I, Au^{III}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cu^{II} was suppressed with 100 mg of cyanide to less than 2%. The percentage extraction of Mn^{II} and Ru^{III} was decreased to below 2% by precipitating them with bromate solution and SO₂-water respectively. Sn^{II} was removed by precipitating Ca^{II} with NaOH leaving Sn^{II}

in solution prior to the extraction of Ca^{II} . Pt^{IV} and Zr^{IV} were suppressed with 100 mg of thiosulphate and by addition of H_2O_2 respectively to less than 10%. The percentage extraction of Eu^{III} , La^{III} , In^{III} , Sc^{III} , Fe^{III} , Fe^{II} , Ce^{III} and Ce^{IV} was decreased to below 2% by precipitating them as hydroxides using ammonium chloride and ammonium hydroxide prior to the extraction.

The stoichiometry of the extracted species was determined by the method of substoichiometric extraction. A plot of amount of Ca^{II} taken vs the activity of the organic aliquot gave a linear relationship until it is sub-equivalent to the reagent added, after which it remained constant. A break occurred at the stoichiometry of Ca^{II} : alizarin in the ratio of 1 : 2. The stoichiometry of metal to reagent was further supported by the slope-ratio method.

A 2.18 mg of Ca^{II} was back-extracted to better than 98% with 20 ml of 1 : 1 HCl.

Experimental

All the chemicals and reagents used were of A.R. grade. A stock solution of Ca^{II} was prepared by dissolving appropriate amount of calcium oxide in HCl. ^{45}Ca and the isotopes used for studying the cation interference were provided by B.R.I.T., Trombay. Solutions of the cations and anions were prepared by dis-

solving the appropriate salts in distilled water to give the desired concentration. Acid was added wherever necessary. Alizarin was used without further purification.

The isotopes were counted such that β -emitters were counted on an end-window type G.M. counter in conjunction with a decade scaler, high voltage unit and a timer and γ -emitters were counted on a γ -ray spectrometer in conjunction with a 3.5 cm \times 3.5 cm NaI(Tl) flat-type detector.

General extraction procedure : To a solution (1 ml) of Ca^{II} containing Ca^{II} (0.82 mg) labelled with ^{45}Ca , a 0.25% alizarin in methanol (10 ml) was added. The pH of the solution was adjusted with NH_3 and then equilibrated with 1-octanol (20 ml) for 8.0 min. Both the organic and the aqueous phase was allowed to separate. An aliquot (2 ml) of each phase was taken in a planchet, evaporated and counted on a G.M. counter.

This separation procedure was applied for the radiochemical separation of calcium from neutron irradiated targets of normal, benign and cancerous tissues of the human brain.

Reference

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